

Research Paper

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**Public Space as an Urban Cultural and Tourism Education Facility
with a Historical Atmosphere****(Case Study: Old City Area of Jakarta)****Silviana Amanda A Tahalea¹, Erlina Novianti¹**¹*Department of Photography Faculty of Art and Design Universitas Trisakti, Jakarta, Indonesia***Abstract**

The Old City area, which is a part of Jakarta City has become the symbol of Batavia's historical greatness. Batavia is also known as the Queen of The East due to its beauty (Brill, 1993). From its long historical record and the abundant number of historical heritages, Old City area revitalization efforts have become a priority in DKI Jakarta Governor's work programs. Based on Law Number 26 Year 2007 regarding Landscapes, Jakarta should own 30% of green open spaces in its administrative area. However, Jakarta only provides 10% of green open (Hariyawan et al., n.d.). The small amount can also be seen in the Old City area with a small portion of green open space or public area. The Old City area of Jakarta is now filled with illegal dwellings and abandoned buildings which are often used by migrant communities as their residences. This situation creates irregularity and discomfort for the people. Old City area is a cultural heritage area, which is often utilized as a gathering area for artists with routine activities such as photographers, mural artists, and theatrical actors. However, these communities often face difficulties due to limited facilities in the area. Based on the policy analysis of historical cultural heritage preservation of the Old City area in Jakarta, we can conclude that revitalization efforts aim to provide public open spaces by optimizing their functions, and comforts, while also bringing back the historical heritage atmosphere. The goal of this design is to shape interaction space patterns that are in accordance with the local art communities so that they can have their own working spaces. The method utilized in this research was a qualitative descriptive and case study methods, which were implemented in the Old City area. The revitalization of the Old City area in Jakarta has the potential to improve it as urban tourism and art education, which is also integrated with green open space that functions as social space. The involvement of communities in the area is also important in assisting the organizing, driving, and supervising efforts of public areas.

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Keywords*Public area; art education; urban tourism; historical heritage.***1. Introduction**

The Old City of Jakarta (Indonesian: *Kota Tua Jakarta*) is known as a reflection of the historical heritage of the founding of the city of Jakarta, the transfer of power from the two kingdoms and the colonial period left heritage buildings that should be preserved. The efforts of the DKI Jakarta Government in maintaining historical buildings in the Old City area have never stopped. Revitalization is a priority for every governor of DKI Jakarta in charge. The Old City of Jakarta is located in West Jakarta which is also a business center because it is adjacent to Chinatown, where most of the people trade. Based on data from the DKI Jakarta Government, the Old City area (Old Batavia) was once a symbol of glory. This area has undergone several changes in power. Those that once controlled this area were the Tarumanegara Kingdom, the Sunda-Pajajaran Kingdom, the Banten-Jayakarta Sultanate, the VOC, and the Dutch East Indies. The existence of the Sunda Kelapa port as the main gateway for the entry of merchant ships at that time made the Old City a center of the economy. The Old City was located close to the Sunda Kelapa port – an entry

point for merchants from various countries. However, it was also the entry point of the colonizers into Batavia. This area then developed towards the center of current West Jakarta.

The discourse to revitalize the Old City of Jakarta as a tourist space has been promoted for a long time. Efforts to revive and make the Old City a heritage tourism area have been carried out by holding various events both on a national and international scale in this area. According to the results of a preliminary study by the researchers, the Old City is now experiencing serious problems. Some of its areas are now disorganized, slums, and have lots of squatters. In addition, thuggery often occurs in this area. This causes inconvenience to the surrounding community because this area becomes scary and indirectly loses its beauty. Referring to the results of the policy analysis, the objective of the policy to support the preservation of the historic environment of the Old City of Jakarta is to create a public open space by optimizing function, user comfort, and regional continuity with a maritime image because it is located in the Sunda Kelapa Port zone surrounded by heritage buildings (Dewi, 2009). According to Dewi, based on the Draft of the Master Plan of the Old City of Jakarta published in 2007, the area consists of 5 zones, namely as follows.

- a. Sunda Kelapa Zone,
- b. Fatahillah Zone,
- c. Chinatown Zona,
- d. Pekojan Zone, and
- e. Rejuvenation Zone.

Special areas in these zones have a higher historical value than other areas in the radius of the Old City of Jakarta because those areas are highly limited in their development. The problems are that the area is disorganized & slum, has lots of illegal dwellings, and lacks public green open space that can be used for activity, education, and tourism facilities. According to data from the Indonesian Environmental Forum (Indonesian: *Wahana Lingkungan Hidup Indonesia* (WALHI)), one of the largest environmental movement organizations in Indonesia, the number of public open spaces in Jakarta has only reached 9% of the minimum 30% of green land that is ideally possessed by a city. Based on these data, Jakarta lacks public green open space. Everyone on this earth undeniably makes use of public spaces after leaving their homes. They may use sidewalks, streets, parks, and open spaces between buildings that function to connect those buildings. Public space is an area where we also often spend time in everyday life. However, designers or architects in most cases only think about the main building. Things outside the main building sometimes get neglected or are only considered after the main building is completed. Despite that, in the current era, many changes have occurred. Many people have paid attention to the comfort of public spaces and take advantage of them as areas to rest and work.

According to Gaventa (2006:31), public spaces include plazas, streetscapes, walkways, parks, and others that can be adapted to the needs of the local community and can be used by the general public. Public space is an open space, which is a location that is planned because of the need for meeting places and joint activities in the open area. Public space is part of an environment that has a pattern. Principally, public space can be considered as a place that can accommodate certain activities of humans both individually and in groups.

To create a city that has characteristics, humanism, and spirituality are not only limited to spatial planning and city buildings because if they are the only thing that becomes the main point, then the characteristics of a city will be lost, just creating a metropolis with silence. To realize a city that grows and develops into an education center, an information center, a growth center, a center of change, a center of appreciation, and a center for the development of moral values, its citizens must have basic human qualities. These qualities will become the main points to establishing human civilization. These basic qualities are as follows.

- a. The city must be inhabited by a community of philosophers whose young people formulate concepts of ideology, constitutional conceptions, and other philosophical sciences,
- b. Whose artists have creativity and characteristics that will shape the character and characteristics of society,

- c. Whose technocrats will influence the development of the economy, improve the political system, and accelerate the growth of life in a better direction based on science and technology, and
- d. Whose businessmen tend to influence the urbanization process quickly by expanding their wings in trade and services in urban areas by building offices, factories, and other business centers.

Urban planning is also related to spatial planning which includes economic, social, and cultural factors which are usually not related to the visual quality of the environment. Activities carried out in urban areas are also diverse, and divided into formal and informal activities. The examples of formal activities are as follows.

- a. Commercial activities, which include various trade scales, such as stalls, kiosks, markets, shops, supermarkets, and malls.
- b. Residential activities, which include various types of housing and settlements from simple houses to luxury homes.
- c. Industrial activities, which include small, medium, and large industries.
- d. Public activities, which include various buildings or land used for the public interest.

The Intan City Park area is a historic urban area. This area is still part of the Old City of Jakarta. This area is in the process of being revitalized by the DKI Jakarta Government to restore the existing historical nuance. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the design of new buildings that act as one of the conservation efforts with the concept of historic urban areas. According to Alexander Papageorgiou (1970) in the book “*Continuity and Change: Preservation in City Planning*”, there are two criteria to determine an area a historical urban area, namely as follows.

- a. Uniqueness in its urban composition, and
- b. Architectural quality and geographical locality.

Furthermore, the aspects that need to be preserved and protected from an area that is part of a cultural heritage area are aspects of historic monuments that have historical, scientific, and cultural meanings. According to Sir Bernhard Feiden (1994) in the book “*Conservation of Historic Buildings*”, in the context of conservation, several things also need to be considered, namely as follows.

1. Damage prevention with good maintenance, supervision, and management.
2. Efforts to preserve the original condition. Thus, the construction or repair must refer to the original condition.
3. Consolidation of the physical materials of a building. In principle, it is an effort to strengthen the building's resistance to damage.
4. Restoration: efforts to rebuild in line with its original forms based on evidence of the authenticity of forms, materials, and designs.
5. Rehabilitation: efforts to maximize the usefulness of building functions. One of the methods is adaptively changing the building so that it can be used with new, more modern functions.
6. Reproduction: attempts to replace parts of historic monuments that have been damaged or lost.
7. Reconstruction: an effort to rebuild a building or place that has been lost or heavily damaged based on sufficient evidence.

Based on the fulfillment of city quality points and urban activities, the role of the artists is very important in terms of creativity and the characteristics that will shape the character and characteristics of the society. Therefore, in this study, the authors will discuss the design of green open public spaces in the Old City of Jakarta so that it can be used as an area of art education and tourism for the people of Jakarta.

The Old City of Jakarta is a heritage area that continues to attract the attention of the people of Jakarta to visit. However, the physical condition of this area still needs a lot of improvement in terms of facilities and infrastructure to meet the criteria of a city with excellent characteristics. In the area of the Old City of Jakarta, we can easily find the activities of art communities, such as painting communities, photography communities, and music & theater arts communities. However, these communities do not have the facilities to carry out their activities although they are

also the main attraction of the Old City. Therefore, the authors are interested in providing facilities for this active art community so that people can learn art and witness art activities.

Figure 1. The exciting condition of Kota Tua Jakarta

(Source : https://www.atmago.com/berita-warga/relokasi-pkl-kota-tua-ditargetkan-rampung-2016_d4f4b5ba-f290-4b6b-abfd-f23becb86ae7)

According to expert research, this kind of facility is necessary for urban people to remain optimistic and attached to the values that are being promoted in a place. The event that has proven this argument is the "Sunday Morning" event in Yogyakarta. Therefore, the Old City area needs to be revitalized by involving the artistic community, especially those from the local community. This collaborative concept is often referred to as community-based tourism. In this concept, the community is involved in the design of the area, particularly related to earning income, job opportunities, and the preservation of the environment and local indigenous culture which in turn fosters the identity and pride of the local people (Setyaningsih, 2015).

To respond to this revitalization discourse to become an integrated tourist area and maintain the historical values of the glory of the city of Jakarta in the Batavia era, it is necessary to create a public open space by optimizing function, user comfort, and regional continuity by carrying a maritime image with its suspension bridge and the Sunda Kelapa port zone (Euis Puspita, 2009). Considering many complex problems stated above, this study attempts to analyze the potential of four main aspects in revitalizing the Old City. The four aspects include the role of mural painting in public space, the role of informative signage, the incorporation of vintage visual elements with colonial patterns, and green open spaces as places for art education and tourism while maintaining the colonial theme as a form of preserving heritage elements.

Figure 2. Kali Besar, Kota Tua, Jakarta

(Source: <https://travel.okezone.com/read/2021/02/09/406/2358996/asyiknya-berwisata-di-kota-tua-jakarta-ini-sederet-pilihan-destinasinya>)

The purpose of this design is to form a pattern of interaction space according to the character of the local community and the millennial generation so that this generation is interested in getting to know the culture and character of a place. In the process of designing the spatial pattern, communal characteristics, and regional patterns in the Old City become the basis or inspiration for creating a public green open space concept, in which its design must be in harmony with the theme of the Old City area. Based on the problems identified, the research team limited the problems to the design of the area. Some of the problems that become the research focus are the physical aspects of building architecture, aesthetic aspects of the design, and tourism aspects related to changing the irregular environmental functions in the Old City into a tourist area. In more detail, the problem in this study is formulated in the following points: (1) How to restore the historical value of the Old City by converting historical heritage buildings into new landmarks and tourist focus in Jakarta? (2) How to create a public space that can facilitate the local art community?

2. Public Space

Concerning open space performance facilities that can be used for routine artistic events, the role of the public space has been further investigated based on the theory of the role of the public space, as put forward by Carmona *et al.* (2008), namely as follows.

- a. Economy:
 - Giving a positive value to the property value.
 - Boosting economic performance.
 - Being able to be a good business.
- b. Health:
 - Encouraging people to be active in physical movement.
 - Providing information and formal space for sports activities.
 - Reducing stress.
- c. Social:
 - Providing space for social interaction and learning processes for all ages.
 - Reducing the risk of crime and anti-social behavior.
 - Encouraging and improving community life.
 - Encouraging intercultural interaction.

In terms of its function, public space can facilitate the need for meetings and joint activities, allowing meetings between humans to interact and carry out joint activities while bringing up a creative process. According to Utami Munandar (1999), one of the things that encourage the creative process can come from within us or from the surrounding environment. Here, the environment is a public space that can inspire ideas for its users to do productive things in a creative process. In addition, public space must have several criteria, namely the ability to work and generate new creativity. Moreover, public space must also be able to be a place to show or exhibit creative works so that these works may get direct appreciation from the public.

In line with the government's plan to make the Old City area a cultural tourism destination, Intan City Park as a part of the Old City has considerable potential to fulfill the plan. The attractiveness of the bridge in the Intan City Park is often expressed with the phrase "*Het Indische Bouwen*" meaning a combination of modern Western structures and techniques with local and traditional forms. Because of being surrounded by colonial-style buildings that have beauty and splendor, the area has an attraction to be developed with a colonial-style concept. By considering the existing reality, the Intan City Park area is plausible to be transformed into a tourist area. By reviving this area, it is expected that it can form a pattern of interaction space that is in line with the character of the existing local community and the millennial generation so that this generation can be interested in getting to know the culture and character of a place. In the process of designing spatial patterns, communal characteristics, and regional patterns in the Intan City Park area become the basis or inspiration for creating a space concept, in which its design must be in harmony with the Intan City Park area or the location around the revitalization area. The place can be designed to introduce the culture

and character of a place through an art activity so that it can become a place for performances and education that share experiences. Through this design, the introduction of tourist characteristics and visitors in a certain place can be increased. The concept of working with the community is often also called community-based tourism. In this concept, we can directly involve the community in the area design process, especially related to earning income, job opportunities, and the preservation of the environment and local indigenous culture which in turn fosters the identity and pride of the local people that grows as a result of increased tourism activities (Setyaningsih, 2010:20).

Community-based tourism is a sustainable development by embracing the community as the main actor through community empowerment in various tourism activities. Therefore, the maximum benefit of tourism is intended for the surrounding community so that it will not cause friction with the local community. The main target of the cultural-based tourism concept is the development of tourism and improving the welfare of local communities (Arifin, 2017:122).

The use of open space is as follows:

- a. Private open space: an open space that only certain people can access, such as a yard.
- b. Common open space: an open space that can be accessed by anyone.
- c. Linear open space: an open space in the form of lines, such as boulevards, streets, and pedestrian walkways.

Many countries in the world are starting to increase open space or public space as part of the construction of an area or building. One of the reasons is that global warming has become a topic that is often discussed. Many activities carried out by humans contribute to increasing the effects of global warming. For this reason, scientists and artists have begun to pay attention to the material in the process of making a product to be more environmentally friendly. Likewise in the field of architecture, architects have begun to design buildings and use sustainable and environmentally friendly materials which are commonly referred to as eco-friendly.

This eco-friendly design pays great attention to the concept of technology and space utilization for the public interest. According to Edwards (2001:27), the concept of eco-friendly buildings usually supports a healthy lifestyle both physically and mentally, such as paying attention to airflow, making lots of air ventilation, and getting lots of sunlight. Space utilization strategies, both for cultivation areas and protected areas, need to be done creatively. This is one step to reducing temperature changes both locally and globally.

According to Gehl (2008), public spaces must be able to provide protection, comfort, and enjoyment. Meanwhile, Carr *et al.* (1992) provided important points for an ideal public space, namely as follows.

1. Comfort: the main point that encourages a person to decide whether to use/live in a public space or not.
2. Relaxation: the fulfillment of needs that include mental comfort. To achieve this need in urban areas, ecological elements (e.g., trees, plants, and water) can become the main factors that can support a person to relax.

Figure 3. Plaza

(Source: <https://www.archdaily.com/943348/v-plaza-urban-development-3deluxe>)

The recommendation above depicts a casual atmosphere to enjoy an open space that has ecological elements. We may see a seating level with a modern, integrated, friendly, and eco-friendly urban atmosphere.

3. Passive Engagement: the need for a person to enjoy the surrounding public space without having to always be involved in direct interaction with other users. Elements that support the creation of passive engagement can be in the form of performances, exhibitions, interesting murals, or other interesting activities.

Figure 4. Kumulo 1
(Source: <https://manual.co.id/directory/kumulo/>)

The recommendation above is a facility that can be provided for the community so that they can enjoy public space without having to be involved in direct interaction with the people around them. Activities that can be done are watching music practice, paying attention to the art community sketching, and others.

4. Active Engagement: the need to involve direct physical experience with the place and people. This need is in the form of social interaction which involves direct contact, either with friends, family, or the existing community.

Figure 5. Kumulo 2
(Source: <https://manual.co.id/directory/kumulo/>)

Figure 5 is a compound facility located in Kumulo, BSD. A compound is a separate building that is located close together as a place to hold workshops or regular meetings for local communities. In this compound, the community can be actively involved in regular training or workshops organized by the existing communities. This compound can also be used as a business space for the surrounding community.

5. Discovery: the desire to try new experiences provided in a place. This need can be in the form of concerts, festivals, art exhibitions, theaters, markets, community activities, and others which are usually seasonal. A good public space can invite individuals to have activities in that space.

Figure 6. Public plaza

(Source: <https://www.pinterest.com/ngaichuen/urban-design-public-space/>)

Figure 7. Kumulo Flex Space

(Source: <https://manual.co.id/directory/kumulo/>)

Figure 7 is a terraced open space facility that can be used to sit and watch performances or other activities organized by the local community. There is also a flex space or function room that is large enough to hold larger events, such as exhibitions, seminars, study rooms, and other community gatherings.

Considering the economic point of view proposed by Carmona *et al.* (2008), an area should also give a positive value to the property and encourage economic performance. If it is associated with the science of architectural photography, the planning of buildings that are attractive and aesthetically pleasing from a photographic point of view also needs to be considered. Architectural photography has an important role in the socialization and introduction of an area to the general public. If an area is built thematically, then the area can become an aesthetic photographic object. Thus, the photos obtained from the area can increase property values, making the area possess the potential to become a tourist area.

Considering the development of digital photography and social media nowadays, the aesthetic value of a building and area has a big influence on someone's desire to take pictures of the building object. Like the Old City with colonial-themed buildings that attract many tourists and become a photographic object for many communities, the Intan City

Park area can also be projected to be the same as the Old City of Jakarta. This is because the role of photography specifically architectural photography is very large in promoting an area.

Another example that we can analyze is the Chinatown culinary area (Pantjoran) PIK which is a culinary area with an interesting concept. Visitors can feel directly the atmosphere of Chinatown which is very thick with many decorative lanterns, murals, and ornament details that represent Chinese culture. Some of the murals and the ornaments displayed are intended to educate the public about Chinese culture. Thematic buildings like this attract a lot of visitors to come either to enjoy culinary delights or just take pictures for social media purposes.

Figure 8. Gate of Pantjoran PIK

(Source: <https://www.kompas.com/food/read/2020/11/23/161412175/pantjoran-pik-resmi-dibuka-destinasi-kuliner-baru-di-jakarta-utara?page=all>)

Social interaction is the essence of social life because, without interaction, there can be no life. Social interaction in the public space creates a sense of community, as seen from the role of the public space based on activities in the public space. The presence of a planned public space will create the dynamics and effectiveness of the utilization of the public space. One of the activities that can bring the dynamics to life is art activities involving the art community.

One component of society that can support the dynamics of public space is the art community. The art-and-culture community is one of the most active types of community, has a lot of mass, and has the potential to revive an area. For this reason, the authors need to document the art communities in the Intan City Park area so that these communities can help revive existing public spaces. The design of public spaces is expected to be in line with the character of the existing local community so that it can later be managed organically by the local community. Some of the advantages of involving local communities in the management of public spaces are:

1. Planning for the procurement of facilities is good and adequate to meet the needs of the community in the Intan City Park area.
2. Organizing the use of public space facilities is more regular and on target because local people know best about their needs.
3. The movement of activities is easier because all activities that run should be for the entertainment and convenience of the local community.
4. Supervision of the use/licensing and maintenance of public spaces is usually one of the most difficult obstacles to overcome if it is left to a supervisory unit. Conversely, if it is carried out together with community involvement, it will be easier.

The presence of the communities can also revive the tourism potential in the Intan City Park area. Community-based tourism has a better chance of being able to develop sustainable and periodic small-scale tourist objects and attractions. Therefore, it can be managed by local communities and entrepreneurs, making it have a minimal socio-cultural impact and a greater chance of being accepted by society. With the involvement of local communities in the management of the area, it is expected that it will reduce the complicated bureaucracy and illegal fees that usually occur in many tourist attractions and public places in Jakarta. Eventually, this will have an impact on the enthusiasm

of other communities outside the area to organize or join local communities so that the atmosphere becomes more dynamic.

Empowerment of local communities in this area is very useful in increasing tourist attraction or the local community and the general public involvement through activities they carry out regularly. In addition, historical buildings around the area indirectly also empower the community through the tourism sector and contribute to improving the local community economy. According to Arida (2016:35), community empowerment through the tourism sector is a process of building and restoring people's confidence that they can build their local and cultural potential to become a tourist attraction in meeting basic needs and achieving a better life that develops continuously and sustainably.

The local communities in the area around Intan City Park and the Old City of Jakarta have different backgrounds of involvement. Some of them participate spontaneously. Some others involve themselves due to encouragement. Based on data that the authors obtained unofficially or from the results of searching on digital search engines, the local communities categorized as spontaneous participants are the Manusia Batu Community (established in 2013), Lingkar Rupa Community (established in 2010), Pencak Silat Cakra Buana Community (established in 1978), Sunda Kelapa Heritage Community (established in 2012), Chinatown Art-and-Culture Community (established in 2015), and Sahabat Budaya Community (established in 2011). Meanwhile, the local communities categorized as encouraged participants are Paguyuban Onthel Wisata Kota Tua and Jelajah Budaya Community. The presence of Paguyuban Onthel Wisata Kota Tua was encouraged by the Local Working Group (LWG) which was established by the Destination Management Organization (DMO) for the Old City in 2012. Meanwhile, the presence of the Jelajah Budaya Community was encouraged by the Mandiri Museum in 2005. Data on local communities that are officially registered with the DKI Jakarta Government were not found by the authors. It would be better if these communities were officially registered with the relevant agencies.

The DKI Jakarta Government has indeed planned to make the Old City a center for education and arts by revitalizing the PPI building on Jalan Malaka which is widely known as the Cipta Niaga building which has become a place for art, music, theater, and film communities by collaborating with academics from Jakarta Institute of Arts (Indonesian: *Institut Kesenian Jakarta*). This collaboration with academics is to ensure that the program activities held are of high quality and sustainable. This can also be applied in the open space of the Intan City Park area by embracing the local art community and academics. Thus, the activities held will be more focused and sustainable. For this reason, official data are highly needed, especially those concerning the art community in the Intan City Park area. One of the art communities is the Perupa Kota Tua Community which is a group of painters who usually paint and sell their paintings along the sidewalks in the Glodok area. It will be more orderly if the community is given adequate space in the Intan City Park area to make the open space in this park livelier. The Perupa Kota Tua Community can collaborate with academics in the arts to create activity and training programs for the local community and the general public so that the aspects of the economy, education, and arts are fulfilled. Opening public spaces to facilitate formal art classes for academics is also a good step to fulfilling discovery and active engagement points from public open spaces.

3. The Concept of Supporting Facilities

Supporting facilities that may promote water recreation areas are those that make people relaxed and enjoy the surrounding view, such as the following.

- a. Garden chairs along the river with materials that are suitable for their designation.
- b. Garden lights with several types of shapes that match the characteristics of water recreation facilities. In addition to serving as artificial lighting at night, they also have aesthetic elements.
- c. The cleanliness system which requires special handling to keep the environment clean by providing trash cans at several points.
- d. Signages that are designed to provide information, placed in a strategic location (e.g., road intersections), and made with materials that are in line with the design theme.

Landscape systems for supporting water recreation facilities by providing the impression of being one with nature. It can also function as a guide and improve natural beauty at the same time (Hendrawaty, 2017).

4. Recommended Outdoor Spatial Concept

As discussed in the concept of open space and the criteria for green open space that meet the basic standards, the authors make recommendations for the realization of green open spaces in the Intan City Park area where there is idle land from PT. KAI that can be used as a public green open space that can facilitate the activities of the local art community, thereby attracting tourists with routine activities from the community. The recommended locations are as follows.

Figure 9. Location of green open space

(Source: Personal documentation)

Figure 9 is the location of the green open space to be placed. Green open space is set in this area because it is very close to the iconic location of the Old City, namely the Intan City Park Bridge, making people able to enjoy green open space while visiting the icons and historical relics of the Old City area. The location of the open space is also set next to the Kali Besar canal, making it close to the ecological element in the form of water flow which is expected to meet the relaxation criteria. Undeniably, the Kali Besar Canal needs a revitalization effort by the DKI Jakarta Government so that it is more comfortable for users of green open spaces. The extensive area of green open space also helps fulfill the percentage of green open areas that should be based on the provisions of the Directorate General of Spatial Planning, which is 30% of the total area.

The authors recommend that green open spaces must be able to facilitate the art community in the Intan City Park area so that the community can carry out activities in the green open space. Activities in open spaces will also be more dynamic if the art community can make regular programs, not only as a means of recreation but also as a means of art education. The 10 is an image of green open space recommendations to meet the green open space standard criteria according to Stephen Carr: active engagement, passive engagement, and discovery.

Figure 10. Green open space recommendation

(Source: Personal documentation)

Active engagement activities can be fulfilled by having a compound area as a secretariat or activity center for the art community. In this compound area, the art community can hold small-scale training or exhibit their work. Bench areas for drawing together or learning to sketch can make green open spaces for users to interact. In Jakarta, there are quite many schools or higher education institutions that have art lessons or art and drawing courses so the facilities provided by this green open space are expected to accommodate their needs. The authors also recommend having a flex space or a large multipurpose room that can be used as areas of study, seminars, and exhibitions for the art community and other art education institutions. This flex space can also be managed for commercial and educational purposes. Art exhibition activities can invite people’s attention to come to appreciate artworks while enjoying green open space facilities. Enjoying art exhibitions can facilitate passive engagement criteria and the art activities carried out can be an element of discovery for visitors.

Figure 10 is a recommendation to facilitate the stage art community and to meet the criteria of active engagement, passive engagement, and discovery.

Figure 11. Green open space recommendation

(Source: Personal documentation)

Figure 11 is the recommended design for a mini outdoor amphitheater. This facility can accommodate the needs of the music, theater, and dance communities in the Intan City Park area. Regular performances from the community can invite art activists and the public to visit. When not having a show, this amphitheater can be used as a seating area for visitors. In addition, this area can also be used as a drawing area for art activists.

As we know, open-space performance areas are rarely found in Jakarta. In other words, this facility is undoubtedly an attraction for this green open space.

Figure 12. Green open space recommendation

(Source: Personal documentation)

Figure 12 is a recommendation for green open space to meet the criteria for green open space standards according to Stephen Carr, namely active engagement, passive engagement, and discovery. The wall behind the compound area and flex space can be used as an open-space mural. This mural or wall painting activity is also one of the activities favored by students, young people, and art activists. Mural images have also been widely used as decorations in commercial places. This open-space mural will also invite the attention of the wider community, especially as a tourist attraction. With the proliferation of selfie culture and the need to upload content on social media, a facility like this can certainly attract the attention of many visitors. This open space area can also be used as a means of education and practicing drawing murals for local communities and other art institutions in Jakarta.

The authors also provide recommendations to continue to include elements of architectural decoration and thematic green open-space interiors. Due to the location of the Intan City Park which is still an integral part of the Old City area, the colonial decoration elements can be used to remain united with the colonial nuance that is thick in this area.

Figure 13. Green open space recommendation

(Source: Personal documentation)

Figure 13 is a recommendation for green open space to meet the standard criteria for green open space according to Stephen Carr, namely relaxation and comfort. More sitting areas, sports facilities, and playgrounds can be provided in this area. In general, exercising is one of the reasons why people go to open spaces or parks. The children's play area is also a facility that should be provided considering the lack of a children's play area in the Intan City Park area. In this area, ecological elements can be added to support the feeling of relaxation when visiting the park, such as shady trees that suit the climate in the area around Intan City Park. Elements related to water such as fountains or fish ponds can also support feelings of relaxation.

To realize an ideal green open space, it must involve many elements such as the landscaping section. If this recommendation is approved, the authors will collaborate with many qualified institutions in the field of landscaping.

5. Conclusions

Recommendations to restore the historical value of the Old City through converting historical heritage buildings into new landmarks and tourist locations in Jakarta by presenting public spaces must be able to provide protection, comfort, and enjoyment for visitors and people living near the area.

The recommendations are to create public spaces that can facilitate the local art community by presenting space as an area to make unforgettable experiences and evoke memories of the architectural beauty of colonial-style buildings with iconic forms of historic aesthetic visual elements. For this reason, public space planning must be carried out in an integrated manner by involving the local community. The involvement of existing communities to help organize, mobilize, and supervise the use of public spaces can make activities in public spaces occur regularly so that public spaces may become comfortable for the public to visit.

The Intan City Park area is a historic urban area. It is still part of the Old City of Jakarta which is an area that is in the process of being revitalized by the DKI Jakarta Government to restore the existing historical nuance. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the design of new buildings, which becomes one of the conservation efforts, by considering the concept of historic urban areas. In the Intan City Park area, it is planned to build a mixed-use area that has the potential to become an entertainment and tourism area. Here, the entertainment area is a public space that can serve as a social space that can invite many people from outside to visit. Public space is an open spot, which is an area planned because of the need for meeting places and joint activities in the open air. Public space is also part of an environment that has a pattern. Principally, public space can be considered as a place that can accommodate certain activities of humans both individually and in groups.

The development of public spaces must also pay attention to the material used, thereby making the final results more environmentally friendly. The eco-friendly design is very suitable for the concept of public facilities by taking into

account the concept of technology and space utilization for the public interest. For this reason, public space planning must be carried out carefully by involving the local community. The involvement of the existing communities is also important to help organize, mobilize, and supervise the use of public space. The community also may make activities in public spaces occur regularly so that public spaces become comfortable for the public to visit. In addition, public space must also be able to be a place to show or a place to exhibit creative works so that they get direct appreciation from the community.

Considering the economic point of view proposed by Carmona *et al.* (2008), an area should also give a positive value to the property and encourage economic performance. If it is associated with the science of architectural photography, the planning of buildings that are attractive and aesthetically pleasing from a photographic point of view also needs to be considered. If an area is built thematically, then the area can become an aesthetic photographic object. Thus, the photos obtained from the area can increase property values, making the area possess the potential to become a tourist area.

One component of society that can support the dynamics of public space is the art community. The art-and-culture community is one of the most active types of community, has a lot of mass, and has the potential to revive an area. Empowerment of local communities in an area is very useful in increasing tourist attraction or the local community and the general public involvement through activities they carry out regularly. In addition, historical buildings around the area indirectly also empower the community through the tourism sector and contribute to improving the local community economy. Opening public spaces to facilitate formal art classes for academics is also a good step to fulfilling discovery and active engagement points from public open spaces.

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References

- Arida, Nyoman Sukma. 2016. *Dinamika Ekowisata Tri Ning Tri di Bali*. Denpasar: Pustaka Larasan.
- Arifin, A. P. R. (2017). Pendekatan Community Based Tourism Dalam Membina Hubungan Komunitas Di Kawasan Kota Tua Jakarta. *Jurnal Visi Komunikasi*, 16(01), 111-130.
- Carmona, R. ; Martins, C. R., 2010. Physical quality, viability, and dormancy of recently harvested Melinis minutiflora P. Beauv. seeds. *Rev. Bras. Sementes*
- Carr, Stephen, Mark Francis, Leanne G. Rivlin, and Andrew M. Stone. 1992. *Public Space*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Edwards, Brian. *Green Architecture*. JohnWiley&Sons.London. UK
- Euis Puspita, Dewi, 2009, Analisis Ruang Terbuka Publik Bersejarah dalam Rangka Revitalisasi Kota Tua Jakarta, Repository Scientific IPB, Bogor, <https://repository.ipb.ac.id/handle/123456789/4352>
- Firdaus, Fauzi,et.all, 2018, Revitalisasi kawasan Kota Tua Jakarta dengan Alternatif Konsep TOD, Jakarta: Universitas Muhammadiyah Jakarta., *Jurnal Arsitektur PURWARUPA*, Vol. 02 No 1, Maret 2018.
- Gaventa, Sarah. 2006. *New Public Space*. Octopus Publishing. London
- Hendrawaty, Diah, 2017, Taman Wisata Alam di Kawasan Green Belt,Gajah Mungkur, Wonogiri , Penekanan pada Penataan Fasilitas Wisata dengan pendekatan Arsitektur Organik sebagai Penunjang Kegiatan Wisata Wonogiri, <file:///E:/Desain%20Taman%20Air%20Gajah%20mungkur.pdf>
- Pengembangan Perkotaan, 2011, Definisi Kota dan Kawasan Perkotaan, <https://pengembanganperkotaan.wordpress.com/2011/11/09/definisi-kota-dan-kawasan-perkotaan/>

Tahalea/ The Academic Research Community Publication

Puspita, Euis Dewi, Analisis Ruang Terbuka Publik Bersejarah dalam Rangka Revitalisasi Kota Tua Jakarta, 2009, Bogor: Sekolah Pascasarjana Institut Pertanian Bogor.

Hariawan, D., Direktur, S., Ruang, P., Agraria, K., Ruang, T., Raden, J., & No, P. I. (n.d.). *PLANNING FOR INDONESIAN HERITAGE CITY*.

Setyaningsih, w., 2010, Food Trucks yang Makin Digemari – Community Based Tourism, Solo: UNS Press – Koran Sindo., <https://lifestyle.sindonews.com/berita/1012378/152/food-truck-yang-makin-digemari>.

Utami Munandar. 1999. Pengembangan Kreativitas Anak Berbakat. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.